

Chemical Constituents of *Eupatorium erythropappum* : Eupathronoside—A New Flavanone Glucoside and (-)-1S,2R,4S,5R-2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-menthane— A New Monoterpene Diol

SUNIL K. TALAPATRA*, MILAN K. PAL, ASOK K. MALLIK** and BANI TALAPATRA*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

A new flavanone glucoside designated as eupathronoside (1) and a new monoterpene diol shown to be (-)-1S, 2R, 4S, 5R-2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-menthane (3) have been isolated from the whole plant of *Eupatorium erythropappum* Robinson along with kaempferyl 5-methyl ether (4), (+)-3S,4S,6R-3,6-dihydroxy-*p*-menth-1-ene (5), physcion (6), coumarin, methyl *p*-coumarate and β -sitosterol. Eupathronoside has the structure as 3,4'-dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone-5-*O*- β -D-glucoside (= 7-*O*-methylaromadendrin-5 β -D-glucoside).

IN continuation of our studies on Asteraceae plants of *Eupatorium*^{1,2} and *Anaphalis*³⁻⁵ genera, we undertook the chemical investigation of *Eupatorium erythropappum* Robinson, a shrub native of Mexico and introduced in Tibet, China and Darjeeling District (West Bengal). The isolation and characterisation of a new flavanone glucoside, a new monoterpene diol, kaempferyl 5-methyl ether and five other known compounds have been presented in this paper.

Eupathronoside, C₂₂H₂₄O₁₁, m.p. 233°, isolated from the ethanol extract, has been assigned the structure 1 (3,4'-dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone-5-*O*- β -D-glucoside = 7-*O*-methylaromadendrin-5- β -D-glucoside) from spectral and chemical evidence. It exhibited ir bands for OH (3 600-3 000) and flavanone C=O (1 667 cm⁻¹). Although eupathronoside gave no colouration with FeCl₃ solution, the presence of phenolic OH group was apparent from the bathochromic shift of the absorption maxima with dilute alkali [λ_{\max} (EtOH) 228 (3.38) and 282 (4.19); λ_{\max} (EtOH+KOH) 238 (4.33) and 285 nm (log ϵ 4.25)]. Its ¹H nmr spectrum (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) indicated the possible presence of a 3,5,7,4'-tetraoxygenated flavanone and a sugar moiety. The signals at δ 3.85 (3H[†], bs, OCH₃), 4.95 (1H, dd, *J* 11.5 Hz and 5 Hz, 3-H)[†], 5.65 (1H, d, *J* 11.5 Hz, 2-H), 6.80 and 7.05 (2 \times 1H, bs, 6-H and 8-H) and 7.35 and 7.85 (2 \times 2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, B-ring protons) were assigned to the flavanone moiety and those at δ 3.85 (2H[†], bs, CH₂OH), 5.10-6.70 (1H, m) and 5.95 (1H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, anomeric proton) to the sugar moiety. Most of the protons were shifted downfield possibly due to solvent effect.

[†] Actually a (6H, brs) was observed at δ 3.85.

- (1) R = H; R₁ = β -D-glu.
(2) R = Ac; R₁ = β -D-glu(Ac)₄.

Eupathronoside was hydrolysed with dilute HCl to form D-glucose and 7-*O*-methylaromadendrin, m.p. 187°. That the β -anomer of D-glucose was involved was evident from the coupling constant of the axial anomeric proton⁷. On acetylation (Ac₂O-Py), eupathronoside formed a hexaacetate, m.p. 223°, (*M*⁺ 716), [α]_D -44.77° (CHCl₃). The ¹H nmr spectrum (200 MHz, CDCl₃) of the latter exhibited signals at δ 2.00, 2.02, 2.03, 2.06 and 2.12 (5 \times 3H, s, 5 \times OCOCH₃, four in the glucose moiety and one at C-3), 2.32 (3H, s, one phenolic acetate, 4'-OCOCH₃), 3.82 (3H, s, 7-OCH₃), 4.22-4.28 (2H, m, -CH₂OAc of the glucose moiety), 4.98-5.46 (5H, m, 4 \times CHOAc of the glucose moiety + the anomeric proton), 5.31 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz, 2-H), 5.61 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz, 3-H)[†], 6.25 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, 8-H), 6.52 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, 6-H), 7.16 (2H, 2 \times t,

** Present address: Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032.

$J_{2',9'} = J_{6',8'} = 9$ Hz and $J_{2',6'} = 3.1$ or 2.1 Hz, 2'-H and 6'-H⁸ and 7.49 (2H, $2 \times t$, $J_{3',2'} = J_{5',6'} = 9$ Hz and $J_{3',6'} = 2.1$ or 3.1 Hz, 3'-H and 5'-H)⁸. The signals due to the protons of the flavonoid part of the hexaacetate are comparable with those of the respective protons of 7-O-methylaromadendrintriacetate⁹. Moreover, the absence of any 4'-methoxy group was evident from the fact that the B-ring protons of 4'-methoxy flavanones⁶ appear as a broad singlet at δ 7.10-7.20. The *trans* orientation of 2-H and 3-H was consistent with their coupling constant¹⁰. The OCH₃ group was placed at C-7 as irradiation of its signal caused nuclear Overhauser enhancement of both the *meta*-coupled aromatic proton signals [δ 6.25 (8-H) - 36%, and 6.52 (6-H) - 12%]. The glucosyl moiety is therefore located at C-5. The unequal enhancement of the signals of 6-H and 8-H may be either due to preference of the OCH₃ group for a particular conformation¹¹ (*i.e.* CH₃ directed towards 8-H) or due to interaction of 6-H through space with the CH₂OAc protons of the glucose moiety (the enhancement being less than that of 8-H) or due to both factors. Thus, the hexaacetate can be assigned the structure 2. The mass spectrum of the hexaacetate exhibited characteristic fragment ion peaks at m/z 386 (M^+ - anhydroglu(Ac)₄), 344 (386-CH₂CO), 331 (ion *a*), 326 (386-HOAc), 234 (344-HOAc or 326-CH₂CO) and 169 (ion *b*)⁸.

(-)-1S,2R,4S,5R-2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-menthane (3), m.p. 174°, C₁₀H₂₀O₃ (M^+ 172), $[\alpha]_D - 77^\circ$ (CHCl₃), isolated from the ethyl acetate extract exhibited ir band (3 400-3 100 cm⁻¹) for OH group. Its ¹H nmr spectrum (80 MHz, CDCl₃) showed signals at δ 0.82 and 0.93 (2 × 3H, d, J 7 Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 0.99 (3H, d, J 5 Hz, 1-CH₃), 1.11-2.22 (7H, m, 3 × CH₂ + CH), 3.45 (1H, bs, $w_{1/2} \sim 16$ Hz, 5-H_(ax)¹²) and 3.82 (1H, bs, $w_{1/2} \sim 9$ Hz, 2-H_(eq)¹²). Hydrogenation (Pd/C) of (+)-3S,4S,6R-3,6-dihydroxy-*p*-menth-1-ene (5) isolated from this plant, afforded 3 as the major product. The m.p. and $[\alpha]_D$ values of 3 were in good agreement with its identity as the enantiomer of (+)-1R,2S,4R,5S-2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-menthane, reported to be formed in the hydroge-

nation of (-)-3R,4R,6S-3,6-dihydroxy-*p*-menth-1-ene¹⁸. Compound 3 will have the preferred conformation 3a. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of 3 resembled closely to that of 5-hydroxyterpin-1-ene¹⁴.

Kaempferyl 5-methyl ether (4), m.p. 215°, C₁₆H₁₂O₆, has been isolated from the ethyl acetate extract. It gave yellow colouration with alcoholic KOH, green colouration with FeCl₃¹⁵ and purple colouration in Shinoda test (Mg/HCl). The uv absorption maxima in ethanol and their NaOAc and AlCl₃ induced shifts were comparable to those reported in the literature¹⁶. The ir spectrum showed bands for OH (3 600-3 100 cm⁻¹) and flavone C=O (1 660 cm⁻¹). The ¹H nmr spectrum (80 MHz, DMSO-d₆) exhibited signals at δ 3.82 (3H, s, 5-OMe), 6.30 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 6-H), 6.68 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, 8-H), 6.90 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, 3'-H and 5'-H) and 8.05 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, 2'-H and 6'-H). The chemical shifts of the aromatic protons are very close to those of some 3,5,7,4'-tetraoxygenated flavones^{17,18}. The OCH₃ group has been allocated to C-5 as the ¹H nmr spectrum lacked any low field proton beyond δ 10 for chelated OH^{19,20}. Moreover, the compound underwent demethylation on refluxing with ethanolic 6N HCl (a condition for selective demethylation of the 5-OCH₃ group of polymethoxy flavones²¹). The demethylation product was identified as kaempferol by direct comparison with an authentic sample²².

(+)-3S,4S,6R-3,6-Dihydroxy-*p*-menth-1-ene (5), isolated from the ethyl acetate extract of the plant, was identified from its spectral (ir, ¹H nmr and mass) data and by direct comparison of its diacetate with an authentic sample²³. The melting point and $[\alpha]_D$ values of 5 also agreed well with those reported for this compound and its enantiomer^{18,24-25}. The preferred conformation is shown as 5a. It may be mentioned here that this is the second report of the natural occurrence of 5, the first one being from *Eupatorium macrocephalum*²⁶. The other known compounds were identified from their spectral data and/or by direct comparison with authentic samples.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries in an electrical metal-bath and are uncorrected. The uv spectra were measured in aldehyde-free ethanol with a Varian 634 S spectrophotometer. The ir spectra were run in KBr pellets on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. The ^1H nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ on Varian CFT-20 (80 MHz) or JEOL FX-100 (100 MHz) or JEOL FX-200 (200 MHz) spectrometer with SiMe_4 as internal standard. The mass spectra were run at 70 eV using a direct insertion probe and optical rotations in CHCl_3 . The silica gel used for column chromatography was of 100-200 mesh, unless otherwise stated, and tlc was done on silica gel G. Petrol refers to light petroleum, b.p. 60-80°.

Extraction : Dried and powdered whole plant (800 g) of *E. erythropappum* Robinson, collected from Darjeeling, West Bengal, during the winter of 1981, was extracted in the cold with petrol, EtOAc and EtOH. The concentrate of the petrol extract did not exhibit any intense spot on tlc and therefore was not investigated. The EtOAc and EtOH extracts, each showing several intense spots on tlc, were separately chromatographed over silica gel (60-100 mesh) using solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity. Similar fractions as indicated by tlc (silica gel G) were combined.

Compounds from EtOAc extract :

Physcion (6) and β -sitosterol : The reddish brown residue from the C_6H_6 elutes was rechromatographed over silica gel using petrol- C_6H_6 (1 : 9). The earlier fractions afforded physcion (4 mg), crystallising from CHCl_3 -petrol as fine red needles, m.p. 205° (lit.²⁷ 207°), δ (80 MHz, CDCl_3) 2.42 (3H, s, 3- CH_3), 3.91 (3H, s, 6- OCH_3), 6.66 and 7.34 ($2 \times 1\text{H}$, d, J 2 Hz, 7-H and 5-H), 7.05 and 7.59 ($2 \times 1\text{H}$, bs, $w_{1/2} \sim 3$ Hz, 2-H and 4-H), 12.08 and 12.28 ($2 \times 1\text{H}$, s, exchangeable with D_2O , chelated phenolic OH at C-1 and C-8). The later fractions furnished β -sitosterol (10 mg), crystallising from CHCl_3 -MeOH as flakes, m.p. 137°.

(+)-3*S*, 4*S*, 6*R*-3, 6-Dihydroxy-*p*-menth-1-ene (5) : The CHCl_3 elutes on concentration gave a residue containing colourless crystals. Recrystallisation from CHCl_3 furnished 5 as fine colourless needles (20 mg), m.p. 165°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 33.8$ (CHCl_3 , c , 0.062); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 450-3 000 (OH), 1 470, 1 390, 1 370, 1 080, 1 035, 1 000, 995, 875 and 710 cm^{-1} ; δ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) 0.85 and 0.98 ($2 \times 3\text{H}$, d, J 7 Hz, 4- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.24-2.20 (4H, m, $\text{CH}_2 + 2 \times \text{CH}$), 1.80 (3H, s, 1- CH_3), 3.60-4.05 (2H, m, 3-H and 6-H) and 5.51 (1H, bs, $w_{1/2} \sim 7$ Hz, 2-H); M^+ m/z 170; diacetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$) : liquid, laevorotatory; δ (80 MHz, CDCl_3) 0.80 and 0.89 ($2 \times 3\text{H}$, J 6.8 Hz, 4- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.67 (3H, s, 1- CH_3), 2.05 (6H, s), 5.05-5.28 (2H, m) and 5.54 (1H, s, 2-H) - very close to the data provided by Pascual-Teresa²⁸.

Kaempferyl 5-methyl ether (4) : The concentrate of the CHCl_3 -MeOH (99 : 1) elutes on rechromatography using the same solvent mixture gave a yellow

solid (7 mg) which on crystallisation from MeOH- CHCl_3 afforded 4 as yellow needles, m.p. 215°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 230 (4.19), 267 (4.18), 296 (4.02) and 370 (4.26), λ_{max} (EtOH+NaOAc) 230 (4.22), 270 (4.20), 327 (4.07) and 375 (4.22), λ_{max} (EtOH+ AlCl_3) 230 (4.28), 269 (4.29), 351 (4.89) and 421 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.18); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 600-3 100 (OH), 1 660 (flavone C=O), 1 610, 1 590, 1 500, 1 415, 1 350, 1 330, 1 220, 1 190, 1 175, 1 160, 1 120, 1 090, 980, 850, 830, 815, 790 and 700 cm^{-1} .

Demethylation of 4 : Compound 4 (3 mg) was refluxed with ethanolic 6 *N* HCl (1.5 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and then extracted with EtOAc. The extract on concentration gave a residue which was identified as kaempferol by co-tlc with an authentic sample²⁹.

(-)-1*S*, 2*R*, 4*S*, 5*R*-2, 5-Dihydroxy-*p*-menthane (3) : The residue from the CHCl_3 -MeOH (19 : 1) elutes on rechromatography over silica gel afforded 2, crystallising from EtOAc-petrol as fine colourless needles (7 mg), m.p. 174°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 77^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.020), m/z 172 (M^+ , 11.95%), 154 (1.9), 139 (6.84), 136 (4.94), 121 (11.44), 111 (14.54), 93 (12.99), 86 (3.28), 72 (100.0), 71 (19.0), 68 (7.64), 53 (6.84) and 43 (33.10).

Compounds from the EtOH extract :

Coumarin and methyl *p*-coumarate : The concentrate of the C_6H_6 elutes exhibiting two major spots in tlc was rechromatographed over silica gel. The petrol- C_6H_6 (1 : 4) elutes gave coumarin (12 mg) as colourless needles (CHCl_3 -MeOH), m.p. 70°. The C_6H_6 - CHCl_3 (1 : 1) elutes furnished methyl *p*-coumarate in colourless needles (CHCl_3 -petrol) (20 mg), m.p. 137°; gave yellow colour with ethanolic KOH.

Eupathronoside (1) : The yellowish gummy mass from the CHCl_3 -MeOH (19 : 1) elutes on further chromatography (silica gel) using CHCl_3 -MeOH (9 : 1) as eluent gave a white solid which on crystallisation from MeOH- CHCl_3 afforded eupathronoside (1) as colourless needles (12 mg), m.p. 233°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 228 (3.38) and 282 (4.19); λ_{max} (EtOH+KOH) 238 (4.33) and 285 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.25); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 600-3 000 (OH), 1 667 (flavanone C=O), 1 600, 1 440, 1 370, 1 300, 1 260, 1 212, 1 165, 1 100, 1 040, 1 020, 990, 950 and 830 cm^{-1} (*p*-disubstituted benzene).

Eupathronoside hexaacetate (2) : Eupathronoside (4 mg) was acetylated with $\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$ at room temperature and the product obtained by usual work-up was crystallised from CHCl_3 -petrol when the hexaacetate (3 mg) was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 223°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 44.77^\circ$ (CHCl_3 , c 0.022), λ_{max} (EtOH) 222 (4.99) and 280 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.76); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 790 (C=O of 4- OCOCH_3), 1 730 (C=O of other OCOCH_3), 1 642 (flavanone C=O), 1 600, 1 540, 1 400, 1 265-1 230, 1 060, 940-930 and 860 cm^{-1} ; m/z 716 (M^+ , 16.5%), 388 (6.7), 387 (28.1), 386 (40.5, 7-methoxy-3,4'-di-*O*-acetyldihydrokaempferol), 345 (12.3), 344 (22.8, 386- $\text{CH}_2\text{C}=\text{O}$), 332 (5.24), 331 (33.78), 170 (9.5), 169 (100), 167

(13.37), 136 (11.36), 127 (13.69), 109 (50.86) and 43 (74.51).

Hydrolysis of eupathronoside: Eupathronoside (2.5 mg) was refluxed with ethanolic 2 N HCl (2.5 ml) for 3 h. EtOH was then removed from the reaction mixture under vacuum with occasional addition of water (3 × 2 ml) and the residual liquid was extracted with EtOAc (2 × 5 ml). Glucose was detected in the aqueous part by pc (n-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O, 4 : 1 : 1) and the aglycone was obtained from the EtOAc extract in very low yield (0.5 mg), m.p. 187°.

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